

The Influence of Leadership behavior and Training on Employee Performance Mediated Employee Achievement Motivation

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze whether the influence of leadership behavior on employee performance is mediated by the achievement motivation of employees of shopping center companies, with a sample of 126 employees. The data analysis method uses *structural equation modelling-partial least square (SEM-PLS)*. The results showed that leadership behavior has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, leadership behavior has a positive and significant effect on achievement motivation, training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, and achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating leadership behavior on employee performance and Achievement

motivation has a positive and significant effect on mediating training on employee performance.

Keywords:- Leadership behavior, Training, Achievement Motivation, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The object of this analysis is the-second oldest shopping center company in Pekanbaru. The author collects information on the company's performance for the period 2017 to 2021 in Figure 1 Figure 1. shows a decrease in average employee performance from 2019 to 2021. Therefore, it is necessary to increase employee performance to achieve the target of visitor visits.

Fig 1 Average Graph of Employee Performance Appraisal

In interviews with general managers and HRD managers about what factors influence employee performance, it was found that the most influential variables were leadership behavior, training, and achievement motivation.

To strengthen the emerging variables, researchers conducted a preliminary survey of variables that influenced employee performance with 20 employees, as listed in the following tables.

Table 1 Results of the Preliminary Survey of Leadership Behavior

No	Questions	Disagree	Agree
1	The leader asked me for feedback for performance improvements/improvements	(4) 20%	(16) 80%
2	My leader sympathized with me when NoI had difficulties in my work	(8) 40%	(12) 60%
3	The leader clearly describes the new vision that the company needs	(10) 50%	(10) 50%

Source: Preliminary Survey Results (2021)

Table 2 Results of the Training Preliminary Survey

No	Questions	Disagree	Agree
1	Training makes me confident	(4) 20%	(16) 80%
2	Training makes me feel secure about my position	(5) 25%	(15) 75%
3	Training makes me feel responsible with my duties	(3) 15%	(17) 85%

Source: Preliminary Survey Results (2021)

Table 3 Results of the Preliminary Survey of Achievement Motivation

No	Questions	Disagree	Agree
1	I need a challenge at work	(3) 15%	(17) 85%
2	I need teamwork	(5) 25%	(15) 75%
3	I want to be influential in the team	(4) 20%	(6) 80%

Source: Preliminary Survey Results (2021)

Table 4 Results of the Preliminary Employee Performance Survey

No	Questions	Disagree	Agree
1	I worked beyond the allotted time	(6) 30%	(14) 70%
2	I try to develop my potential.	(5) 25%	(15) 75%
3	Saya selalu memenuhi target pekerjaan saya	(3) 15%	(17) 85%

Source: Preliminary Survey Results (2021)

Related to the variables above, here are the research gap findings from previous studies on leadership behavior styles, training, and achievement motivation for employee performance.

Table 5 Previous Research Gap Analysis

No	Researchers	Variable	Analysis Results
1.	Lemuel and Antonio (2019)	1. Leadership Behavior (X1) 2. Employee performance (Y)	positive and insignificant
2.	Kartikal Yuliantari, Ines Pralsalsti (2020)	1. Leadership behavior (X1) 2. Employee performance (Y)	positif dan signifikan
3.	Ningsi, Alhabsji and Utama (2015)	1. Training (X2) 2. Employee performance (Y)	positive and insignificant
4.	Yuyun, Supharta and Rahyuda (2017)	1. Training (X2) 2. Employee performance (Y)	positive and significant

Source: Data processed by the author

From table 5, we can see that each of them has a positive and significant effect, as well as negative and insignificant effects. Therefore, it can be explained by adding achievement motivation variables to be used as mediating variables from the analysis, which will be compiled in the form of a thesis with the title "The Influence of Leadership and Training Behavior on Employee Performance Mediated by Employee Achievement Motivation in Shopping Center Companies."

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Leadership Behavior

According to Abdul Azis Wahab, as quoted by Mashudi (2017), behavior is a leadership style in implementing leadership functions, which, according to this theory, is very influential and decisive in making the organization effective in achieving its goals. Meanwhile, according to Amin (2016), leadership behavior is an individual's response as a motivator in an organization to an

action that can be observed and has a positive or negative impact on the organization.

Yukl (2012) identified categories of leadership behavior and classified them into three meta-categories, namely task-oriented behaviors, relationship-oriented Behaviors and change-oriented behaviors.

➤ *Training*

According to John H. Proctor and William M. Thornton in Sedarmayanti (2017: 187), training is a deliberate act of providing tools so that learning can be carried out [9].

According to Paramita (2018), this means that training will shape employee behavior in accordance with what the company expects, for example in accordance with company culture [7]. According to Azlansyah (2019), training is not only useful for increasing employee knowledge in improving their work results, but will also have an impact on increasing the results to be achieved by the company [3].

➤ *Achievement Motivation*

According to Samsudin (2019: 281), motivation refers to the process in which external variables influence or give impetus to people or working groups, encouraging them to participate in defined activities [8].

According to McClelland (2013: 103), people who have a strong motivation to perform show six special features. These factors include a clear desire to perform, a high sense of individual responsibility, a willingness to engage in strategic risk-taking, the formulation of achievable goals, the creation of comprehensive working strategies, and a firm will to realize their goals. In addition, these people show a proactive approach by seeking real feedback aggressively in all their efforts and actively pursuing opportunities to implement their well-designed plans.

➤ *Employee Performance*

Performance is the result of the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee as a whole, which can be used as a basis to determine whether individual work is good or vice versa (Arianto and Kurniawan, 2020) [2]. Aksinapang and Idris (2018) explained that employee performance refers to a person's achievements measured based on standards and criteria set by the company [1]. According to Gharib, Jamil, Ahmad, and Suhail (2016), employee performance can be described as an individual's

ability to achieve employee work goals in accordance with the achievement of organizational expectations and goals [4].

According to Mangkunegara (2016), performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him [6]. Employee performance is a measure that can be used to determine the comparison of the results of task implementation and responsibilities given by the organization in a certain period and can be relatively used to measure work performance or organizational performance (Shanty and Mayangsari, 2017) [10]. According to Koopmans et al. (2014), employee performance consists of three dimensions: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. Hypothesis development in this study is [5]:

- H1: The Effect of Leadership Behavior on Employee Performance
- H2: The Effect of Leadership Behavior on Achievement Motivation
- H3: The Effect of Training on Employee Performance
- H4: The Effect of Training on Achievement and Motivation
- H5: The Effect of Achievement Motivation on Employee Performance
- H6: The Effect of Leadership Behavior on Employee Performance, Mediated by Achievement Motivation
- H7: The Effect of Training on Employee Performance, Mediated by Achievement Motivation

III. ANALYSIS METHODS

This research is quantitative, using primary and secondary data as data sources. This study uses a form of causal relationship to identify and explain the influence of independent variables, namely leadership behavior (X1) and training (X2) on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Z), and to test whether the mediating variable, namely achievement motivation (Z), mediates leadership behavior (X1) and training (X2) on employee performance (Y). The population in this study was 126 permanent employees of shopping center companies in Pekanbaru, with all permanent employees as a sample based on purposive sampling techniques. The data analysis method in this study uses SEM-PLS with SmartPLS software version 3.3.3.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Outer Model

➤ Convergent Validity

Based on the results of data processing in the measurement model (outer model), it can be concluded that the loading factor value of all variables is listed in Table 6.

Table 6 Value of Loading Factor All Variables

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Descriptions
Employee Performance (Y)	KK1	0,880	valid
	KK2	0,885	valid
	KK3	0,918	valid
	KK4	0,910	valid
	KK5	0,914	valid
	KK6	0,930	valid
	KK7	0,892	valid
	KK8	0,937	valid
	KK9	0,881	valid
	KK10	0,895	valid
	KK11	0,902	valid
	KK12	0,916	valid
	KK13	0,900	valid
	KK14	0,876	valid
	KK15	0,882	valid
	KK16	0,893	valid
	KK17	0,919	valid
	KK18	0,937	valid
Achievement Motivation (Z)	MB1	0,876	valid
	MB2	0,861	valid
	MB3	0,872	valid
	MB4	0,868	valid
	MB5	0,885	valid
	MB6	0,864	valid
	MB7	0,826	valid
	MB8	0,877	valid
	MB9	0,816	valid
	MB10	0,854	valid
	MB11	0,859	valid
	MB12	0,852	valid
	MB13	0,860	valid
	MB14	0,860	valid
	MB15	0,862	valid
	MB16	0,870	valid
	MB17	0,900	valid
	MB18	0,879	valid
	MB19	0,880	valid
	MB20	0,907	valid

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Descriptions
Leadership Behaviors (X1)	MB21	0,884	valid
	PK1	0,890	valid
	PK2	0,912	valid
	PK3	0,896	valid
	PK4	0,905	valid
	PK5	0,908	valid
	PK6	0,881	valid
	PK7	0,894	valid
	PK8	0,889	valid
	PK9	0,898	valid
	PK10	0,893	valid
	PK11	0,888	valid
	PK12	0,904	valid
	PK13	0,891	valid
	PK14	0,867	valid
	PK15	0,895	valid
	PK16	0,884	valid
	PK17	0,890	valid
	PK18	0,898	valid
	PK19	0,886	valid
	PK20	0,895	valid
	PK21	0,890	valid
	PK22	0,865	valid
	PK23	0,889	valid
	PK24	0,893	valid
	PK25	0,871	valid
	PK26	0,852	valid
	PK27	0,876	valid
	PK28	0,877	valid
	PK29	0,894	valid
	PK30	0,881	valid
	PK31	0,851	valid
	PK32	0,884	valid
	PK33	0,880	valid
	PK34	0,902	valid
	PK35	0,873	valid
	PK36	0,901	valid
	PK37	0,909	valid
	PK38	0,883	valid
	PK39	0,903	valid
	PK40	0,902	valid
	PK41	0,877	valid
	PK42	0,878	valid
PK43	0,882	valid	

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Descriptions
	PK44	0,886	valid
	PK45	0,873	valid
	PK46	0,900	valid
	PK47	0,900	valid
	PK48	0,898	valid
Training (X2)	PL1	0,887	valid
	PL2	0,879	valid
	PL3	0,859	valid
	PL4	0,908	valid
	PL5	0,843	valid
	PL6	0,872	valid
	PL7	0,882	valid
	PL8	0,881	valid
	PL9	0,887	valid
	PL10	0,890	valid
	PL11	0,861	valid
	PL12	0,879	valid
	PL13	0,858	valid
	PL14	0,894	valid
	PL15	0,901	valid

From table 6, it can be seen that the loading factor value for each variable exceeds 0.7. so it can be concluded that all variables used in this analysis are valid.

Tabel 7 Nilai Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Setiap Variabel

Variable	Nilai AVE	Criteria	Description
Leadership Behavior	0.789	> 0.5	Valid
Training	0.772	> 0.5	Valid
Achievement Motivation	0.753	> 0.5	Valid
Employee Performance	0.817	> 0.5	Valid

Sumber: Hasil Olah Data Menggunakan Smart PLS

The AVE value for *convergent validity* testing is sufficient for the next test.

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

Cross loading is used to calculate discriminant validity using the criterion that an indicator is considered valid to measure a latent variable if its cross loading value on the latent variable is greater than its correlation value on other variables or dimensions.

Table 8 Cross-Loading for all Variables

Indicators	Employee Performance (Y)	Achievement Motivation (Z)	Leadership Behaviors (X1)	Training (X2)	Description
KK1	0.880	0.691	0.725	0.681	Valid
KK2	0.885	0.694	0.747	0.760	Valid
KK3	0.918	0.734	0.793	0.771	Valid
KK4	0.910	0.740	0.748	0.754	Valid
KK5	0.914	0.748	0.802	0.788	Valid
KK6	0.930	0.739	0.795	0.769	Valid
KK7	0.892	0.687	0.754	0.716	Valid

Indicators	Employee Performance (Y)	Achievement Motivation (Z)	Leadership Behaviors (X1)	Training (X ₂)	Description
KK8	0.937	0.766	0.839	0.802	Valid
KK9	0.881	0.713	0.736	0.730	Valid
KK10	0.895	0.711	0.738	0.763	Valid
KK11	0.902	0.736	0.789	0.747	Valid
KK12	0.916	0.734	0.750	0.780	Valid
KK13	0.900	0.743	0.788	0.803	Valid
KK14	0.876	0.698	0.749	0.721	Valid
KK15	0.882	0.693	0.832	0.753	Valid
KK16	0.893	0.722	0.764	0.727	Valid
KK17	0.919	0.771	0.822	0.769	Valid
KK18	0.937	0.785	0.831	0.792	Valid
MB1	0.739	0.876	0.729	0.666	Valid
MB2	0.679	0.861	0.619	0.614	Valid
MB3	0.685	0.872	0.637	0.647	Valid
MB4	0.675	0.868	0.617	0.613	Valid
MB5	0.675	0.885	0.645	0.680	Valid
MB6	0.680	0.864	0.620	0.651	Valid
MB7	0.623	0.826	0.571	0.585	Valid
MB8	0.783	0.877	0.712	0.659	Valid
MB9	0.602	0.816	0.547	0.502	Valid
MB10	0.684	0.854	0.645	0.619	Valid
MB11	0.777	0.859	0.693	0.707	Valid
MB12	0.636	0.852	0.616	0.554	Valid
MB13	0.654	0.860	0.658	0.613	Valid
MB14	0.683	0.860	0.634	0.678	Valid
MB15	0.737	0.862	0.676	0.704	Valid
MB16	0.703	0.870	0.666	0.640	Valid
MB17	0.725	0.900	0.678	0.682	Valid
MB18	0.721	0.879	0.661	0.700	Valid
MB19	0.697	0.880	0.724	0.664	Valid
MB20	0.734	0.907	0.709	0.678	Valid
MB21	0.747	0.884	0.681	0.618	Valid
PK1	0.754	0.668	0.890	0.721	Valid
PK2	0.791	0.664	0.912	0.776	Valid
PK3	0.771	0.659	0.896	0.740	Valid
PK4	0.775	0.681	0.905	0.768	Valid
PK5	0.761	0.697	0.908	0.717	Valid
PK6	0.759	0.615	0.881	0.728	Valid
PK7	0.758	0.690	0.894	0.706	Valid
PK8	0.747	0.655	0.889	0.715	Valid
PK9	0.769	0.648	0.898	0.734	Valid
PK10	0.792	0.696	0.893	0.720	Valid

Indicators	Employee Performance (Y)	Achievement Motivation (Z)	Leadership Behaviors (X1)	Training (X ₂)	Description
PK11	0.764	0.714	0.888	0.687	Valid
PK12	0.769	0.681	0.904	0.692	Valid
PK13	0.762	0.653	0.891	0.726	Valid
PK14	0.753	0.655	0.867	0.727	Valid
PK15	0.772	0.728	0.895	0.722	Valid
PK16	0.768	0.661	0.884	0.695	Valid
PK17	0.765	0.692	0.890	0.721	Valid
PK18	0.762	0.622	0.898	0.702	Valid
PK19	0.787	0.697	0.886	0.757	Valid
PK20	0.775	0.677	0.895	0.720	Valid
PK21	0.757	0.679	0.890	0.752	Valid
PK22	0.728	0.637	0.865	0.654	Valid
PK23	0.789	0.677	0.889	0.750	Valid
PK24	0.795	0.713	0.893	0.779	Valid
PK25	0.741	0.647	0.871	0.654	Valid
PK26	0.735	0.711	0.852	0.644	Valid
PK27	0.794	0.706	0.876	0.788	Valid
PK28	0.740	0.675	0.877	0.702	Valid
PK29	0.751	0.638	0.894	0.689	Valid
PK30	0.745	0.645	0.881	0.705	Valid
PK31	0.729	0.666	0.851	0.744	Valid
PK32	0.751	0.625	0.884	0.709	Valid
PK33	0.741	0.719	0.880	0.725	Valid
PK34	0.786	0.672	0.902	0.775	Valid
PK35	0.751	0.670	0.873	0.746	Valid
PK36	0.766	0.655	0.901	0.718	Valid
PK37	0.766	0.700	0.909	0.751	Valid
PK38	0.753	0.663	0.883	0.729	Valid
PK39	0.827	0.707	0.903	0.796	Valid
PK40	0.788	0.661	0.902	0.755	Valid
PK41	0.748	0.624	0.877	0.720	Valid
PK42	0.758	0.691	0.878	0.740	Valid
PK43	0.772	0.661	0.882	0.752	Valid
PK44	0.746	0.664	0.886	0.693	Valid
PK45	0.745	0.629	0.873	0.715	Valid
PK46	0.792	0.662	0.900	0.775	Valid
PK47	0.780	0.700	0.900	0.718	Valid
PK48	0.784	0.683	0.898	0.762	Valid
PL1	0.700	0.666	0.698	0.887	Valid
PL2	0.719	0.651	0.716	0.879	Valid
PL3	0.732	0.597	0.706	0.859	Valid
PL4	0.789	0.681	0.746	0.908	Valid

Indicators	Employee Performance (Y)	Achievement Motivation (Z)	Leadership Behaviors (X1)	Training (X ₂)	Description
PL5	0.697	0.635	0.684	0.843	Valid
PL6	0.735	0.637	0.694	0.872	Valid
PL7	0.756	0.668	0.701	0.882	Valid
PL8	0.749	0.675	0.723	0.881	Valid
PL9	0.757	0.652	0.738	0.887	Valid
PL10	0.746	0.662	0.756	0.890	Valid
PL11	0.695	0.643	0.669	0.861	Valid
PL12	0.750	0.653	0.730	0.879	Valid
PL13	0.677	0.574	0.706	0.858	Valid
PL14	0.755	0.696	0.760	0.894	Valid
PL15	0.783	0.681	0.767	0.901	Valid

➤ *Reliability*

Composite reliability aims to test the reliability of instruments in a research model with Cronbach's Alpha 0.6 and *Composite Reliability* 0.7 criteria.

Tabel 9 Nilai *Composite Reliability* dan *Cronbalch's Alpha*

Variabel	Composite	Cronbach	Criteria	Description
Leadership Behavior	0.994	0.994	> 0.70	Valid
Training	0.981	0.979	> 0.70	Valid
Achievement Motivation	0.985	0.984	> 0.70	Valid
Employee Performance	0.988	0.987	> 0.70	Valid

Source: Data Processing Results Using Smart PLS

B. Inner Model

In this analysis, the inner model evaluation, or hypothesis test, is performed in multiple steps: path coefficient evaluation, R² evaluation, effect size measurement of f², Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) validation of the overall structural model, and predictive relevance (Q²) testing.

The employee performance variable has an R² value of 0.825, whereas the accomplishment motivation variable has a value of 0.618. The Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) value > 0.36 indicates that the overall performance of the structural model and the outer model is good. Predictive relevance (Q²) is calculated, and the result is 0.93. Because endogenous latent variables in this analysis model have predictive relevance (Q²) values > 0, explanatory latent variables can predict endogenous variables as explanatory variables, demonstrating that this model is thought to have reverse predictive relevance.

Fig 2 Inner Model Variable
Source: Data Processing Results Using *SmartPLS*

➤ *The Proof of the Hypothesis in this Analysis can be seen in the Results of Data Processing as follows:*

• **Hypothesis 1:**
The effect of the work environment on job satisfaction.

The path coefficient is 0.407 and is positive; T-statistics are 5.073 > t table (1.96); and P-values are 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, H1 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Leadership behavior towards employee performance has a positive and significant influence.

• **Hypothesis 2:**
The Influence of Leadership Behavior on Achievement Motivation.

The path coefficient is 0.452 and is positive; T-statistics are 3.709 > t table (1.96); and P-values are 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, H2 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Leadership behavior towards achievement motivation has a positive and significant influence.

• **Hypothesis 3:**
The influence of the work environment on employee performance.

The path coefficient is 0.301 and is positive; T-statistics are 3.966 > t table (1.96); and P-values are 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, H3 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Training on employee performance has a positive and significant influence.

• **Hypothesis 4:**
The Effect of Training on Achievement Motivation.

The path coefficient is 0.372 and is positive; T-statistics are 3.451 > t table (1.96); and P-values are 0.001 < 0.05. Thus, H4 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Training on employee performance has a positive and significant influence.

• **Hypothesis 5:**
The Effect of Achievement Motivation on Employee Performance.

The path coefficient of 0.124 is positive, and T-statistics are 2.480 > t-table (1.96) and P-values are 0.014 < 0.05. Thus, H6 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that the proven hypothesis 6 states that the influence of leadership behavior on employee performance can be mediated positively and significantly by achievement motivation.

• **Hypothesis 6:**
The Influence of Leadership Behavior on Employee Performance mediated by Achievement Motivation

The path coefficient of 0.124 is positive, and T-statistics are 2.480 > t-table (1.96) and P-values are 0.014 < 0.05. Thus, H6 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that the proven hypothesis 6 states that the influence of leadership behavior on employee performance can be mediated positively and significantly by achievement motivation.

- *Hypothesis 7:*

The effect of training on employee performance mediated by achievement motivation.

The path coefficient of 0.102 is positive, and T-statistics are $2.497 > t\text{-table} (1.96)$ and P-values are $0.014 < 0.05$. Thus, H7 is accepted and Ho is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that the proven hypothesis 7 states that the effect of training on employee performance can be mediated positively and significantly by achievement motivation.

V. CONCLUSION

➤ *Several Conclusions were Drawn from the Investigation and Debate in this Study, Including the following:*

- Leadership behavior is positive and significant for employee performance, with the contextual performance dimension having the strongest effect.
- Leadership behavior is positive and significant for achievement motivation, with creative and innovative dimensions having the strongest effect.
- Training is positive and significant for employee performance, with the contextual performance dimension having the strongest effect.
- Positive and significant training increases achievement motivation, with creative and innovative dimensions having the strongest effect.
- Achievement motivation is positive and significant for employee performance, with the contextual performance dimension having the strongest effect.
- Positive and significant leadership behavior towards employee performance is mediated by achievement motivation, with the contextual performance dimension having the strongest effect.
- Positive and significant training on employee performance is mediated by achievement motivation, with the contextual performance dimension having the strongest effect.

VI. SUGGESTION

➤ *These are some Recommendations that can be Made to Supplement the Analysis's Findings, based on the Analysis's Results of the following Discussion and Conclusions:*

- Companies need to improve leadership behavior in the form of support so that employees focus on positive things on the job.
- Companies need to improve leadership behavior by clarifying roles so that employees are motivated to always pay attention to the directions given by superiors.
- Companies need to improve training because it has been found that employees are less willing to take on extra responsibilities.
- Companies need to improve training to encourage employee freedom in suggesting new job ideas.

- Companies need to consistently provide motivation to eliminate behaviors that are not relevant to company goals (counterproductive work behavior), such as small and negative things.
- For the next analysis, the authors expect further analysis with wider sample coverage. As a way of mediating achievement motivation, the analysis's findings on training variables and leadership behavior raise the possibility that other variables will also have an impact as mediators of employee performance.

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